

Point-to-Multi-Point Coherent Optics on Data Processing Units (DPUs) for beyond-5G Low-Latency Applications

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Abstract: Coherent pluggable transceivers supporting both point-to-point (P2P) and point-to-multi-point (P2MP) optical transmissions could be used with Data Processing Units (DPUs) for cost-effective converged infrastructures including packet, optical, and edge computing resources.

1. Introduction

The demand for converged infrastructures that integrate packet, optical, and edge computing resources is rapidly increasing in today's data centers and metro access networks [1, 2]. To support these converged infrastructures, there is a need for cost-effective solutions that can enable both Point-to-Point (P2P) and Point-to-Multipoint (P2MP) optical transmissions [3]. Smart coherent pluggable transceivers are emerging as a promising technology that can meet these requirements, particularly when integrated within Data Processing Units (DPUs) [4].

In this paper, we provide an overview of the potential of coherent pluggable transceivers to support converged infrastructures within DPUs. We will begin with an overview of the enabling technologies, i.e., DPU and P2P and P2MP smart coherent pluggable transceivers. A discussion on the key expected benefits will follow. Finally, we will provide a possible use case of this technology within converged infrastructures suitable for innovative 5G/6G power-efficient and low-latency solutions.

2. Enabling technologies

2.1. Data Processing Unit (DPU)

A DPU, also called a Smart Network Interface Card (SmartNIC), is a specialized hardware component designed to provide high-speed data processing [5]. Although typically used in data centers, within servers and supercomputers, DPUs are attracting interest for their applicability in edge networking scenarios due to their ability to handle data movement, storage, and processing for large datasets: performing calculations at high speed, and enabling real-time analytic and acceleration of data-intensive applications [6]. Traditional Network Interface Cards (NICs) offer low-level protocol acceleration (e.g., Ethernet) and rely on server Central Processing Units (CPUs) to perform other networking functions. On the other hand, DPUs allow programmability at higher layers and direct performing of advanced in-network functions, freeing processing resources for tenant and application services, as illustrated in Fig. 1(a)—the traditional approach—and in Fig. 1(b)—the proposed solution. The current generation of DPUs includes up to 4 interfaces at up to 400 Gb/s, advanced timing and synchronization, hardware encryption, and embedded security features, as well as up to 16 ARM CPUs for embedded computing operations.

2.2. Coherent P2MP transceivers

Fig. 2 shows the communication concept for high-speed coherent pluggable transceivers capable of supporting P2MP connections. These pluggables generate signals with up to 16 subcarriers per unit, where each subcarrier operates as a dual-polarized 4 GBaud signal (up to 25 Gb/s in case of transmitting 16QAM), amounting to a maximum data rate of 400 Gb/s [3]. High-speed connectivity, however, is not everything; modern architectures and traffic patterns in metro/access networks need to be approached in a robust yet flexible manner. While the former is ensured by mature and proven communication techniques such as coherent transmission and Digital Signal Processing (DSP), the latter

Fig. 1: Traditional NIC-based application processing (a) and full in-network function offload enabled by DPUs (b).

Fig. 2: P2MP coherent transceivers enabled by Digital Subcarrier Multiplexing (DSCM). The draw assumes the transmission of 16QAM with ~ 4 GBd, i.e., 25G per subcarrier.

is enabled by the freedom allowed by DSCM. For example, when the 400G P2MP hub transceiver acts as a transmitter in a downstream scenario (i.e., the communication flows from the hub site to leaf transceivers), since the multi-carrier signal is broadcast to multiple leaf nodes, they can extract a single subcarrier or a group thereof according to their traffic characteristics. For example, in Fig. 2, the different leaf nodes receive data flows ranging from 25G ($1 \times 25G$, leaf #1) up to 100G ($4 \times 25G$, leaf #N). Potentially, this allocation of resources at the transmitter opens the door to dynamic adjustments in terms of subcarriers to better match the ebb and flow of traffic patterns during the day, as there are certain moments when networks have to address more critical scenarios [7, 8]. By operating in this fashion, the 400G hub node can utilize a single transceiver to communicate with up to 16 leaf nodes simultaneously, whereby each node would receive a single 25 Gb/s subcarrier. For an upstream scenario, multiple single subcarriers or groups of subcarriers that may or may not have different origins, are combined into a single multi-carrier signal - see spectrum in Fig. 2. Considering that subcarriers could have different levels of distortions (both linear and non-linear), the robustness and effectiveness of the DSP algorithms is a non-trivial aspect of the design of the P2MP transceiver [9].

3. DPUs equipped with coherent P2MP transceivers for edge networking

In the context of edge/metro networking, Internet Protocol (IP) routers equipped with coherent pluggable modules—IP over DWDM (IPoDWDM)—are driving the design and implementation of low-cost converged packet optical transport solutions that are effectively capable of removing boundaries between different IP and optical network domains. For example, edge-to-cloud interconnection can be implemented using a single router at the edge that performs packet forwarding and long-reach optical transmission without requiring dedicated optical equipment (e.g., transponders), as shown in Fig. 3(a).

DPUs have the potential to further improve the edge-to-cloud continuum by removing the barriers between computing and networking resources, as shown in Fig. 3(a). The delivery of Beyond 5G (B5G) services is indeed driving Telco Central Offices (COs) to host not only networking equipment such as routers, but also edge computing resources. The separation of networking and computing resources comes at a cost: it is power-hungry, expensive (both in terms of Capital Expenditure (CAPEX) and Operational Expenditure (OPEX)), and inefficient with respect to latency, as

multiple Opto-Electro-Optical (OEO) conversions must be experienced in the computing continuum between B5G services and edge and cloud resources (highlighted by red dots in Fig. 3(a)). On the other hand, the benefits of relying on a single piece of equipment for edge computing, networking, and long-reach optical transmission are presented in Fig. 3(b) and will now be discussed.

The first benefit is the reduction of active standalone nodes and intermediate OEO conversions. Fig. 3(b) shows the proposed scenario in which edge computing is provided with a DPU equipped with coherent pluggable, enabling both networking and computing resources in a single platform.

The second benefit consists of reduced latency, since the aggregation of computing and optical networking resources in a single platform with fewer OEO conversions also contributes to reducing the end-to-end latency. Furthermore, the adoption of P2MP high-speed transceivers directly plugged into SmartNICs/DPUs will better support ultra-low latency services towards the access, avoiding/limiting aggregation nodes while leveraging hardware-accelerated in-network functions implemented in the DPUs (e.g., encryption).

Achieving these benefits will require certain developments. First, the technology gaps must be filled. State-of-the-art Quad Small Form Factor Pluggable Double Density (QSFP-DD) coherent transceivers are currently not supported within SmartNIC/DPU. Preliminary investigations can be carried out by leveraging an external switch/board encompassing the coherent transceiver and controlled by the DPU as their pluggable modules. Second, it is necessary to define the underlying working software platform, including the operating system and tools for the deployment of containerized applications (e.g., Sylva platform [10]). Third, a specific analysis of the most relevant acceleration capabilities provided by the DPU is necessary to take full advantage of the features that are of specific interest for the considered metro/edge scenario (e.g., Centralized Unit (CU)/Distributed Unit (DU) functions, and security).

Fig. 3: (a) Traditional approach for routing and computing at the edge, using different networks and computing equipment; (b) Convergence of networking and computing scenario at the edge using a DPU equipped with coherent pluggable transceivers of type P2P and P2MP. Highlighted in red are the O/E/O conversions.

Fig. 4: 5G implementation options with User Plane Function (UPF), CU, DU, and RU located in different sites from national central offices, to regional, local, and cell sites. (a) Traditional approach. Cases (b) and (c) decentralize the implementation of UPF-DU-CU (- Radio Unit (RU)) functions closer to the cell site.

4. Use Case: Converged solution for flexible support of functional splits

The innovative edge computing node equipped with SmartNIC/DPU and coherent pluggable modules is expected to improve the performance of two main types of services: (i) service level for ultra-low latency user applications; (ii) the deployment of 5G functions closer to cell-sites.

The latter service will now be specifically considered, focusing on the implementations of functional split options and evolutions to maximally benefit from the presence of optical transport technology. Fig. 4(a), shows the reference 5G implementation with UPF, CU, DU, and RU located in different sites (from national central offices to regional, local, and cell sites). This approach suffers from two main drawbacks: i) high latency due to user traffic reaching the national/regional Central Office (CO); ii) high power consumption due to a large number of OEO conversions and

electronic processing in each traversed site.

Cases (b) and (c) of Fig. 4 illustrate two approaches that decentralize the implementation of UPF-DU-CU (-RU) functions and move them closer to the cell site, relying on hardware-accelerated solutions (i.e., DPU) that have the potential to perform the required 5G functions in a cost-effective manner. Cases (b) and (c), compared to (a), significantly reduce the experienced latency, since user traffic is handled at the local CO (case b) or at the cell site (case c). Additionally, collapsing the user-plane DU/CU-UP-UPF functions allows some General Packet Radio Service (GPRS) Tunnelling Protocol (GTP) interconnects (F1-U, N3, N9) to be bypassed, reducing latency, computation, and energy. Furthermore, the number of OEO regenerations and electronic processing required (?) is significantly reduced. For example, in case (c), direct and transparent cell-to-cloud interconnection could be achieved in selected cases without intermediate processing or OEO regeneration at local or regional COs.

5. Conclusions

The recent availability of both DPUs and P2MP coherent pluggable transceivers has the potential to enable high-performance packet and optical networking within compact and power-efficient edge computing solutions.

The expected key benefits of DPUs equipped with coherent P2MP transceivers are discussed in the context of edge networking. They include the tight integration of computing and networking resources, the reduction of active standalone nodes, and intermediate OEO conversions, as well as the reduced latency.

Finally, a use case for converged solutions is introduced for flexible support of functional splits of 5G / 6G closer to the user equipment, allowing a direct and transparent 5G core-to-cell interconnection that could be achieved in selected cases without any additional intermediate processing or regeneration of OEO in local or regional Central Offices.

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